

THE INFLUENCE OF MUSIC ON THE HUMAN PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract: The article provides information about the fact that music reflects the emotional experiences of a person, that it has a good effect on emotions, and that its content is also a musical artistic image that expresses mental and physical states, and that music has an effective effect on the human body. This article provides some interesting information about the ability of music to treat mental illnesses other than stress.

Key words: psychological, emotion, art, aesthetic, democritic, etymological, stress, education system.

Introduction.

Music is a form of art that reflects human emotional experiences, thoughts, and imagination through a sequence or set of musical sounds. Its content consists of specific musical artistic images that represent changing mental states. It is no exaggeration to say that music is an art that accompanies a person from birth. If you have noticed, the newborn baby calms down and falls asleep with the music of the mother until a certain period. Adults are mostly accompanied by music and headphones when they are free, doing physical work or just going to a destination. Depending on the mood, listening to a cheerful or quiet song and feeling relieved, feeling as if falling into another world, is probably not a stranger to anyone.

The invisible connection between a person and music is related to its appearance?! According to various sources, music appeared in the early stages of social development. Although there is no concrete evidence about the music of that time, various scientific hypotheses are based on this. For example, the singing of birds, calls of animal companions, emotional tones, labor sounds and calling methods of primitive people are considered the first sources of music.

So, music has been with humanity since ancient times. The effective effect of music on the human body is already known. Ancient Greek physicians used wind instruments to treat their patients. Philosopher Democritus said that the flute emits a sound that is not only good for listening, but also for human health, while the people of the Middle Ages believed that the real purpose of music was to *"glorify God, drive away demons, heal the sick, and create love."*

According to various experiments, music affects not only a person's mood, but also breathing, pulse, blood pressure, and internal and external energy. It has a wonderful power that can take a person out of a stressful situation, increase immunity, have a positive effect on the psyche, and encourage creativity. According to data, sound vibrations cause cells to "echo" and affect physiological processes in the body. Certain rhythms and certain frequencies affect the acceleration or, on the contrary, the slowing down of metabolism in the body. George Diamond, an expert in behavioral physiology, found that depending on the nature of the music, the strength of the listener's muscles also changes.

Greek scientist and philosopher Pythagoras was one of the first people to confirm the significant influence of music on human mental and physical condition. According to Iamblich's "*Life of Pythagoras*", if someone listens to beautiful rhythms and songs, then such a person will receive musical education using melodies and rhythms, human morals and passions will be cured, and the initial harmony of mental powers will be established.

In Russia, the first scientific works on the mechanism of music's influence on people appeared at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. In the works of V.M. Bekhterev, I.M. Sechenov, I.M. Dogel, I.R. Tarkhanov, information appeared about the beneficial effect of music on the central nervous system, breathing, blood circulation, and gas exchange. There are probably countless experiences that a person can feel. But if we evaluate not from the point of view of specificity, but from the point of view of generality, all of them can be divided into two groups: positive and negative feelings.

Good mood, joy, happiness, joy, laughter... The names of experiences that we call good emotions can be continued for a long time. According to a study conducted by the Journal of Positive Psychology, listening to "feel-good" music when a person is in a good mood can help them feel more upbeat. So, positive mood tones will also have a positive effect on a person who is in a good mood. Or, according to another source, in fact, a good mood motivates us to listen to happy songs. It is said that a good mood is the reason why we listen to happy music. Therefore, these two concepts continue to require each other in the process. Music, pain and creativity.

The Hero of Uzbekistan, Abdulla Oripov, wrote this in his poem "Listening to the prayer":

*If that's the case, then the pain itself,
How could the man endure?*

Maybe people listen to the painful melodies and realize that the heartbreaking melodies are actually much heavier than the sorrows in their hearts. There are many studies, observations, and surveys that prove that both types of music are healing for the human soul. In fact, even without them, if each person carefully observes his life, one can see that even one day there are many such examples.

Etymologically, the word stress comes from the English term. Means "tension" or "pressure". The term was coined by the physician Hans Selye in the 1930s, and in the 1950s he published his research on stress. Stress is caused by the condition of a living person or their organs, which require much higher performance than usual, putting them at risk of illness. Thus, stress is the feeling of physical or mental changes that cause frustration, nervousness and anger in a person. Cortisol is the hormone that has the greatest effect on changing physical and mental performance. Several scientists have conducted research on the importance of music in the prevention or treatment of stress. When neuroscientist Daisy Fancourt studies the interaction between stress and music, she focuses on the hormone cortisol in the blood.

Do biological responses to a classical music concert and a pop music concert differ? It turned out that no, cortisol levels were reduced by both types of concerts. Classical music gradually reduces the stress level and we feel relaxed, while a pop concert is a cathartic (a substance that accelerates a certain process in medicine) process, so we experience a whole spectrum of sensations. As a result, both types of concerts help us to be calm. Another interesting article on stress prevention suggests that music can treat other mental illnesses

besides stress. The source also contains ancient information about which musical instrument helps to cure what diseases, and emphasizes that the most useful musical instrument for stress treatment is the violin. Another study with nurses found that listening to music during breaks reduced the prevalence of stress among nurses, a profession long characterized by high levels of stress and burnout.

In this study, participants were divided into two groups. One group listened to soothing music of their choice for 30 minutes, while the other group sat quietly in a chair for the same amount of time. When the results were compared for the two groups, the nurses who listened to the music had lower stress levels, blood cortisol levels and lower heart rates than the sedentary group. In addition, research shows that the tempo of music is very important for the human condition. But we must not forget that our emotional reaction to music depends on our personal experiences and memories. It may be impossible to find magic music that is a universal stress reliever for all of humanity, but we can get closer to understanding exactly what characteristics of music and personal experience influence emotional response.

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